

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE PROBLEMS OF LOCATING THE INDUSTRY IN THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the principles and factors of the location of industrial enterprises, as well as on the distribution of raw materials and social labor.

Reasonable placement of industry in the territory of the country is one of the most important tasks of the construction of the society, and it is a necessary condition for raising and developing the national economy of the republic and every economic district.

It is known that the basic laws of the location of productive forces and industry, which is its most important element, are determined by the method of production. Therefore, in the formation of current market relations, in the placement of all its branches, the state is implementing economic reform, and this is considered its component, and its implementation is determined by the current state and strategic tasks of our national economy.

The location of the industry means its distribution on the globe, as well as in some countries or economic districts.

The location of industrial production represents the forms of its territorial organization and is manifested in the location of enterprises (firms) in administrative and economic districts.

The location of this real sector of the national economy is directly related to the territorial distribution of labor. Territorial division of labor (HMT), which is an element of the social division of labor, in simpler words, is the specialization of different places: the country or regions, districts, cities in the production of various products. As a result, the economic "forecast" of these places is formed and their place in the territorial system is expressed.

HMT in a broad sense - it means the placement of production sectors (networks) depending on factors such as the natural conditions and resources of the region, population, labor and other resources, as well as the size of the regional market, the purchasing power of

the population, the level of development of the infrastructure and communication system.

Rational placement of industrial production - high-speed implementation of the extended reproduction process, efficient use of the country's natural resources in all ways and, as a result, increase of social labor productivity, reduction of product costs in each enterprise, equal development of all economic regions of the country, urban and rural and closing the gap between industry and agriculture allows to increase the country's defense capabilities.[1]

The rational location of industry leads to the location of transport and agriculture, the emergence of new cities and villages, the specialization of certain economic regions in the production of certain products.

Placement of industry across economic regions has a great impact on increasing the efficiency of social production. Continuous achievement of the production process, growth of cost-effective social labor productivity, and improvement of the material and cultural well-being of the population are criteria of economic and social efficiency of placing industrial production.[1]

There are fundamental principles of the location of production, which serve as a scientific basis for the rational location of production forces, in particular, industry, in the country, and the implementation of economic policy. These include:

- placing industrial production closer to the sources of raw materials, fuel and energy, and finally closer to the consumer areas of industrial products;
- rational distribution of labor between economic regions and ensuring the overall development of the economy of economic regions;
- striving to equalize the level of economic development of each region and district;
- basing the defense strategy of the republic on the deployment of industrial sectors;
- establishing mutually beneficial relations in inter-country economic relations, achieving efficiency on the basis of international division of labor, accelerating integration into the world economy;
- taking into account the ecological situation of the area, basing on the normative norms of waste discharge into the environment, etc, when locating industrial enterprises.

It is clear from the above that the location of industrial production close to the source of raw materials and consumer areas is one of the most important principles of rational location of industry. The closeness of the industry to the raw material base implies the possibility of the least expenditure of labor at all stages of processing, from the processing of this resource to the receipt of finished products from semi-finished products. For example, electric power is often developed on a water or fuel basis, the textile industry is located closer to the source of raw materials, and the food industry is located in areas with higher consumption. Bringing the industry closer to the source of raw materials and energy provides an opportunity to attract the resources available in the regions to the field of processing, to determine the reasonable size of enterprises (firms). It reduces long-distance transportation of raw materials, fuel, and finished products, and on this basis leads to considerable savings in social labor.

The location of industry close to raw materials, fuel and energy sources and consumers does not ensure that industrial production is evenly distributed throughout the country. Because production resources are unevenly distributed throughout the country.

Even placement of industry is a qualitative feature of industrial development that is compatible with market economy conditions. But it is not recommended to forcibly place all its

branches in the encountered area. Achieving such equality among the industrial development of regions can in many cases lead to the artificial placement of a number of industrial enterprises in regions where there are no conditions for them, and to excessive costs of social work.

Bringing the industry closer to the source of raw materials and fuel and energy and placing the production evenly across the territory of the country creates an opportunity for intensive scientific and technical development. All-round development of electronicization, computerization of production, wide use of new technologies weakens the dependence of industrial production on the natural-geographic (geographical) environment, creates material and technical conditions for more free (careful) selection of industrial locations. Electronicization and chemicalization attract new materials, production waste, and secondary resources to the field of production. Complex use of raw materials combines different types of production.

Scientific and technical development provides an opportunity to expand geological exploration, to open new deposits of mineral raw materials in different regions of the country. The industrial location plan requires a comprehensive economic rationale for the selection of areas and points where new enterprises and regional production complexes will be located.

The economic efficiency of industrial placement is reflected in social labor productivity. Reasonable division of labor between economic districts and complex development of economy of economic districts serve as an important principle of industrial placement.

Complex development of economy of economic districts leads to specific specialization of regions as a result of mutual division of labor. The specialization of certain economic districts depends on the natural resources available in them and the level of rational use of these resources on the scale of the national economy.

Full and effective use of the country's internal resources requires the specialization of each region in the production of certain types of products on the republican scale, and at the same time, it leads to the development of industries in each region that meet the requirements of this region.

Another important principle of localization of production is the international division of labor formed on the basis of inter-country friendship and mutual economic assistance. Such a division of labor ensures the specialization of industries that have natural and economically favorable conditions for the establishment of a reasonable economic structure and its development in each country.

In the implementation of the above-mentioned principles, the factors affecting the choice of locations for enterprises and regional production complexes are taken into account.^[2] Industrial placement is influenced by natural and technical-technological, demographic, economic, ecological factors, forms of social production organization, means of transport, and the nature of production placement.

Natural factors include: quantity and quality indicators of minerals, hydropower and forest resources, climatic conditions of the area, natural waterways and the location of labor resources. All the above factors must be taken into account with the environmental factor. the current ecological situation requires it. In the mining and hydropower sectors, natural conditions affect the technical and economic performance of enterprises, and the location of enterprises in this sector depends on the location of minerals and hydraulic resources. The

location of ferrous metallurgy and chemical industry enterprises depends mainly on water resources.

There is a strong correlation between the location of population and production. The geographical location of labor resources primarily affects the location of labor-intensive industries. Therefore, labor-intensive industries (instrument engineering, radio engineering, light industry) are not located in sparsely populated areas.

The composition and structure of labor resources and the level of qualification of certain regions are important for the placement of industrial sectors. For example, branches of engineering (automotive engineering, instrument engineering, precision engineering) requiring high skills are located in places where there are such qualified personnel, and light industry requiring women's labor is developed in regions with a dense population and a high supply of female labor.^[3]

Science and technology development is the main factor of settlement of all industries. Chemicalization is increasingly affecting the location of industries. The use of chemical methods reduces the influence of climate on the location of the industry, as a result, it creates conditions for its uniform location throughout the territory of the republic. The location of the industry is also influenced by the nature of technological processes. First, the production technology depends on the nature of the required raw materials and energy, the type and characteristics of the manufactured finished product, and changes in the conditions of transportation of raw materials and finished products. Secondly, the specific characteristics of the region play a decisive role in the choice of the technological process of the enterprises to be located.

Improvements in the technology of extraction of underground resources and the enrichment of raw materials and fuels allow the mining industry to be leveled. Complex automation and computerization of production processes reduces the labor spent on the product. Due to this, it is possible to get great results if enterprises (firms) based on computer technology are placed in sparsely populated areas.

Progressive forms of organization of social production, such as concentration, specialization, cooperatization, and combining, play a major role in the location of industry. As a result of the concentration of production, it is necessary to create a very large base of raw materials and energy for the enterprise's consumption, and to expand the area where the enterprise's products are consumed. As a result, transportation costs increase, and the issue of choosing the location and area of enterprises becomes more difficult. Therefore, at the current stage of the transition to the market conditions, instead of locating large enterprises, it is necessary to take into account the transport factor in the foundation of medium and small enterprises.

Specialization has the same effect on industrial location as concentration, because specialization consists in the consolidation of the production of one type of product. Therefore, as the level of specialization increases, the demand for transport increases. When placing enterprises (firms) in one or another area, the amount of such costs must be taken into account.

The effect of the cooperativeization of enterprises on the location of industry can be seen in the example of the establishment of regional production complexes. The regional industrial complex consists of a number of enterprises characteristic of various industrial

branches, which have long-term cooperative relationships. Without taking into account the factor of cooperation, it is impossible to correctly determine the economic efficiency of the objects or complexes to be placed.

The combination of production has different effects on the location of the industry. Combines are highly integrated enterprises. Therefore, their deployment is similar to embodiment.

Raising the defense capability of the Republic to a higher level is certainly one of the important factors that should be taken into account in the organization of industrial deployment. [4]

Industrial deployment is also influenced by the nature of legacy manufacturing deployment. For example, initially established craft centers, their infrastructure needs to be established in this place or in places close to this area.

Conclusion:

Today, the location of industry remains one of the most urgent issues, therefore, the location of an enterprise or firm is mainly located in areas closer to residential areas, as well as closer to raw materials needed for product production, if it does not affect the health of the population. should be placed. The main reason for this is that it will be less expensive for an enterprise (firm) to attract labor and bring it to the market.

If the enterprise or factory is more harmful to human health, the enterprise should be located closer to the base of raw materials, away from residential areas, and should be built in areas closer to the market.

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